
**bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for
innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of marine and coastal geohazard**

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Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a tectonically sensitive coastal environment

BridgET Project Result 06

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PROJECT RESULT REPORT

06 - Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a tectonically sensitive coastal environment

Introduction

This project result includes two complementary deliverables developed to support geohazard education and digital geoscientific modelling in tectonically active coastal environments.

The first deliverable is a comprehensive report produced by Université de Liège, which documents the process of creating a fully immersive virtual geohazard environment for Santorini Island, a tectonically and volcanically sensitive coastal area. This work was initiated during the Santorini Erasmus+ summer school (October 2022) and includes the integration of multi-source geospatial datasets, including:

- Satellite imagery (NASA, Google Earth)
- Bathymetric data (EMODnet)
- Topographic LiDAR-based models (Forte et al., 2019)
- Geophysical data (from Chatzis et al., 2022)

The final product consists of a seamless 3D model that integrates both subaerial and subaquatic features, developed using ArcGIS Pro and Leapfrog for 3D geomodelling. The model has been adapted for VR exploration using Cesium and is compatible with immersive headsets such as Oculus. It provides users with interactive tools, including a mini-map and orientation interface, enhancing spatial awareness during navigation. A video of the Santorini VR (AR) experience can be found at:

https://www.georisk.uliege.be/cms/c_4823285/en/georisk?id=c_4823285

The model has been tested with students, that experienced an immersive exploration using VR toolkit (e.g. Oculus), during the third project summer school in the Maldives. Questionnaires were also submitted to student to collect information about their perception and evaluation of the toolkit.

The report represents:

- A practical application of geospatial modelling tools in education
- An example of replicable methodology for training and curriculum development
- A fully immersive experience that bridges field data and digital visualisation
- A use case for integrating geohazard awareness with digital innovation

The combination of field-based data collection, geomodelling, and VR technologies offers students a unique opportunity to engage with complex geological systems in an intuitive and scalable way.

In addition, we produced an interactive Story Map for the coastal area of Mt. Etna, Sicily, that showcases the integration of satellite imagery, UAV photogrammetry, bathymetric data, and terrestrial scanning. The platform serves as both a scientific narrative and a visual exploration tool for understanding geohazard dynamics in a volcanic coastal setting, produced using high resolution geospatial dataset. This online resource is available at the following link:

☞ Story Map – Etna Region: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4067a77d69fd4d5e8ea7af3f9bfbbdb9>

List of Deliverables:

Deliverable 6.1: Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a tectonically sensitive coastal environment: Technical Report – Virtual Modelling of Santorini.pdf

Deliverable 6.2: ☞ Story Map – Etna Region:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4067a77d69fd4d5e8ea7af3f9bfbbdb9>

1. Project Result 06 – Deliverable overview

Below is a description of the deliverable produced as part of project result “Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a tectonically sensitive coastal environment”.

Deliverable 6.1 – Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a tectonically sensitive coastal environment: Virtual Modelling of Santorini

Description: A technical report documenting the development of a fully immersive 3D geohazard model of Santorini Island using publicly available and literature-based geospatial datasets, adapted for VR exploration.

Type of Output: Technical Report + 3D Model for Virtual Reality

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document + VR-compatible Model

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: Virtual modeling of Santorini.pdf

Deliverable 6.2 – Story Map – Coastal Geohazards of Mt. Etna

Description: An interactive Story Map showcasing multisource data integration for geohazard assessment in the coastal region of Mt. Etna, including satellite, UAV, and bathymetric data.

Type of Output: Web-based Interactive Story Map

Language: English

Access/Format: Online Platform (ArcGIS StoryMap)

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: [Story Map](#) – Etna Region:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4067a77d69fd4d5e8ea7af3f9bfbdb9>

Deliverable 6.1

Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a tectonically sensitive coastal environment: Virtual Modelling of Santorini

1. Cartographic views produced with GIS software – application to the Santorini study case

The goal of his project was to train students in using different mapping and modelling techniques applied to subaerial and subaquatic environments that also allow for visualisation in virtual reality (VR, or extended reality, XR).

The specific task for Liege University (UoL) was to apply these techniques to the representation of coastal environments connected to islands marked by a higher geological or climatic hazard level. As the island of Santorini was also one target of the Erasmus+ schools, we had proposed to map/model environments related to this island, representing also results from geophysical subsurface information obtained with methods that had been presented to the students during the school in October 2022.

Below we present figures showing elements of Santorini at different scales, first as map views developed with classical Geographic Information Software (GIS software, using here ArcGIS Pro, and Google Earth®), then as 3D geo-models and finally as digital environments that can be represented in virtual reality. Related experiences were also tested during the last Erasmus+ school held in the Maldives with students, scientists and professors.

First, we introduce the target site via classical mapping of surface imagery with GIS, as shown in Fig. 1. Some geographic elements and location of geophysical measurements and sites visited in October 2022 are indicated in Fig. 1a.

Second, topographic and bathymetric data have been collected for the construction of the joint subaerial and subaquatic models. Related data are shown separately in Fig. 2, bathymetric data with resolution of 100 m (downloaded from Emodnet - <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/bathymetry>), and open topographic raster data with 30 m resolution extracted from the NASA Earth surface model.

Actually, as for most regions in the world, also higher resolution data exist for Santorini. For instance, Forte et al. (2019) used LiDAR surface data of 1 m resolution for landslide susceptibility calculations over Santorini. After request, G. Forte provided those data (but available only for the main island, which had to be combined first with the NASA surface data of the other islands), which were then used as basic information for the joint topographic-bathymetric models. Due to the enormous difference between the two resolutions (100 m for subaquatic and 1 or 30 m for topographic data, for subaerial main island and the other islands, respectively) a common resolution of 5 m was selected; thus, the bathymetric information was up-sampled and the topographic data down-sampled, applying kriging and smoothing techniques to correct interpolation problems. However, even with the same resolution, if those two

raster models are combined, Fig. 3 shows that a gap exists between related data, along the coastal contact zone (see also zoom in Fig. 3b).

Figure 1. a) Cartographic view of Santorini with Google Earth® (GE), with indication (by GE) of Santorini main island and neighbouring islands Thirasia and Nea Kameni, and of the highest point of Santorini at 560 m altitude: the monastery of Moni Profiti Iliia. Location of HV ambient noise measurements completed during the 2022 Santorini Erasmus+ summer school. b) Cartographic view of Santorini produced with ArcGIS Pro (using the implemented background image).

Figure 2. a) Cartographic (GIS) view of the 100 m resolution bathymetry model (from <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>) around Santorini. b) Cartographic view of the 30 m resolution NASA Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of Santorini.

Figure 3. a) The 5 m resolution DEM (interpolated from the original 1 m resolution model, for the main island) presented in the paper by Forte at al. (2019) and provided by the corresponding authors, complemented by the 100 m bathymetry model,. As shown by the maps, the 5 m model was only produced for the main island of Santorini. b) The same model with Magnifier window near the eastern coast, to show also the gap between the subaerial and subaquatic surface data.

Figure 4. Comparison between the 30 m resolution NASA model and the 5 m resolution DEM (interpolated from the original 1 m resolution model), complemented by the 100 m bathymetry model. See related Magnifier windows in (a) and (b).

Essentially, notwithstanding the interpolation and smoothing process, the original very high resolution (1 m) of the model provided by Forte et al. (2019) can clearly be seen in the zooms of the maps shown in Fig. 4 (a, for 30 m NASA model, b for the 1 m Forte et al. 2019 model, but for our model both interpolated at 5 m pixel resolution). Note the higher resolution does not at all improve the connection with the 100 m bathymetry model (in Fig. 4 with up-sampled 5 m resolution, shown by bluish colors and greenish in coastal areas).

To join the subaerial and subaquatic models, points were extracted from both the coastal contact zones, so to both sides of the gaps, and were used for zonal interpolation using again kriging and smoothing processing. The results are shown in Fig. 5b, also with 5 m resolution, compared with the original disconnected models in Fig. 5a. Still the zoom in Fig. 5b shows that connection in zones marked by large gaps is clearly highlighted by ‘steps’.

Figure 5. a) The 5 m resolution DEM (interpolated from the original 1 m resolution model), complemented by the 100 m bathymetry model. b) Continuous 5 m interpolated subaerial and bathymetric surface model, combining the 100 m resolution bathymetry, the 30 m resolution NASA (for neighbouring islands), and the original 1 m resolution model provided by Forte et al. (2019). For both maps a Magnifier window is shown on the eastern coast.

Those steps (errors of interpolation due to the large gaps) are the strongest in areas marked by the highest elevation changes, typically near the steep slopes in the southeastern part of Santorini island, while the interpolation almost worked perfectly near the smooth slopes in the northern part, as shown by the comparison between the zooms of the maps shown in Fig. 6.

To this general interpolated surface model (covering subaerial and subaquatic zones without gaps), the surface raster of the sea level was added as shown (using also partial transparency) in Fig. 7b.

Figure 6. Continuous 5 m interpolated subaerial (beige colours) and bathymetric (bluish colours) surface model with Magnifier window shown for the flat northern (a) and steep eastern (b) coasts.

Figure 7. Continuous 5 m interpolated subaerial and bathymetric surface model with legend (a) and added sea level raster (b).

Interestingly, exactly during the Santorini Erasmus+ school, where we had shown to the students how subsurface information related to the volcanic deposits of the last Minoan eruption could be studied with the ambient noise geophysical technique, the Greek team of Chatzis et al. published a paper (Chatzis et al., 2022) presenting a map of the thickness of those deposits, as measured with exactly the same technique. Therefore, we had asked the group of Chatzis to obtain those data for mapping and 3D representation. The map view of those data (with thicknesses ranging from 0 m on the higher rocky parts of Santorini to more than 50 m around those mountains, marked by yellow-orange colours and even more than 100 m, as shown by reddish colours) is presented in Fig. 8b.

Figure 8. Continuous 5 m interpolated subaerial and bathymetric surface model with legend (a) and added Minoan deposit thickness values (b) estimated from geophysical data (published by Chatzis et al., 2022 and provided by the authors).

GIS tools allow also combine various overlying raster information, as here the elevation from the global 5 m surface model with the thickness data from the geophysical prospection, to compute a new raster (using the ‘Spatial Analysis’ tools) – here the elevation of the bedrock surface, corresponding to the topography where no deposits are present (0 m thickness – or where not measured as in the northern and southwestern parts), and to the subsurface level under the deposits where they are present (and have been prospected). The related raster of bedrock elevation is shown by beige (~topographic surface) and bluish colours (elevation of several tens of meters and even > 100 m below the topographic surface) in Fig. 9b.

Figure 9. Continuous 5 m interpolated subaerial and bathymetric surface model with legend and added Minoan deposit thickness values in (a), and with corresponding bedrock depth information in (b).

ArcGIS Pro also allows now for relatively smooth visualisation of those data in pseudo-3D. ‘Pseudo’ as the visualisation of surface data is in 3D, as shown in Figure 10, but the real elevation information of subsurface data cannot be viewed in full 3D. Only the colour code allows to represent such kind of information. To get a full 3D visualisation of such data, ‘3D geomodelling’ tools are necessary, as shown in the following section.

Figure 10. a) Map view of the continuous 5 m interpolated subaerial and bathymetric surface model with legend and bedrock depth information. b) Corresponding 3D ‘Global Scene’ view of the same data produced with ArcGIS Pro, enlarged in (c).

2. 3D geomodelling views of Santorini

The data presented in the geomodel views below have, actually, all been prepared by the GIS tools presented above. Thus, we mainly used the smoother 3D visualisation option of both surface and subsurface data proposed by the geomodelling tools. Fig. 11 first presents the 3D visualisation of the global surface model (joint topographic and bathymetric), together with sea level view (using transparency), and high-resolution remote imagery and zooms on coastal areas of Santorini.

Figure 11. a) 3D view of the continuous 5 m interpolated model of Santorini, covered by high-resolution (~ 50 cm) surface imagery, surrounded by the sea level raster (with scale bar of 5000 m length). b) Corresponding 3D view with transparent sea level raster (and view of bathymetric part). c) The same view with subaerial surface imagery. d) Local 3D view of area in the south of Santorini (see outline in b, c) of the combined interpolated 3D model, complemented by surface imagery in (e, with scale bar of 750 m length).

The main added value of geomodelling compared with GIS, as introduced above, is the representation of subsurface information, such as, in our case, the thickness of the volcanic Minoan deposits. The latter is shown by golden colons in the place of the geophysical measurements in Figs. 12a and 12b (12b combined with surface imagery, and the bedrock level below the deposits and on the mountains shown by the golden surface).

Figure 12. a) 3D view of the continuous 5 m interpolated model of Santorini (with scale bar of 5000 m length). a') Partial view of the same model with colons marking the thickness of the Minoan volcanic deposits as measured by Chatzis et al. (2022). b) Corresponding 3D view with semi-transparent sea level raster and high-resolution (~ 50 cm) surface imagery. b') Partial view of the same model with colons marking the thickness of the Minoan volcanic deposits and the bedrock surface in gold, corresponding to the general surface in the mountainous part, but reaching depths of more than 300 m in the flatter northern and southern part (with scale bar of 2000 m length).

We used the (commercial, like ArcGIS) software Leapfrog for this geomodelling, which also allows for 3D representations of 'sectioned' models as shown by the multiple views in Fig. 13.

Figure 13. a – e) 3D views of sections (with various orientations) across the geomodel, with semi-transparent sea level raster and high-resolution (~ 50 cm) surface imagery, with colons marking the thickness of the Minoan volcanic deposits and the bedrock surface in gold, corresponding to the general surface in the mountainous part, but reaching depths of more than 300 m in the flatter northern and southern part (with scale bar of 3000 m length).

3. Santorini in VR – and survey results from the Erasmus+ Maldives school

Virtual Reality (VR) is the type of technology allowing for fully immersive visualisation of those 3D models. Unfortunately, Leapfrog has not yet implemented this possibility (other similar software, like GOCAD, does – at least partly). Therefore, the same raster and point data had to be prepared again for another digital environment allowing for such immersive visualisation. Google Earth VR® has this ‘immersive’ option that can be viewed with adapted headsets; however, Google Earth VR® does not allow for representation of subsurface or any imported data (while Google Earth Pro® with screen-view does, at least for surface data). An alternative option that we used in the past is using Paraview® or Blender® for the preparation and immersive representation of 3D data – one of the problems with those tools is the representation of high-resolution of surface imagery that requires extremely high computer power. This problem is now partly solved thanks to a new side version of Google Earth® designed for VR, which also allows for adding new data and for viewing subsurface information: Cesium. Figures 14 and 15 show screen views of the immersive Santorini environments: Fig. 14 presents 4 views of the 3D surface and imagery of parts of Santorini, including the volcanic deposit mine in Fig. 14c, which has also been visited during the Santorini Erasmus+ school in October 2022.

These views show also parts of the laboratory where they have been taken; actually, our laboratory has both types of headsets, those allowing for visualisation in pure VR (without viewing of the local real environment) and those allowing for mixed views, combining the immersive model visualisation and the viewing of the real environment, as represented in the scenes of Fig. 14.

Figure 14. a – d) 3D views of the immersive environment created for Santorini, using the Cesium background imagery and surface model, here shown as ‘mixed’ reality model (as elements of the surrounding laboratory room are seen).

In addition, we had asked Professor C. Papazachos to provide the results of their ambient noise survey, published in Chatzis et al. (2022), as point data with information about the thickness of the underlying volcanic soft deposits. As within the 3D geomodel, those are also represented as colons (here with rectangular section), as shown below in Fig. 15c. Additionally, a menu appears in the immersive environments that allows the user to select different options as shown in Fig. 15a.

During the survey taken at the Erasmus+ Maldives school (see Table 1 in the annex 6.1) where answers to questions about the general feeling of the users in the immersive environment were collected among students and teachers, we explored in particular the comparison to other “3D” systems (e.g. Google Earth) and GIS tools, and about possible improvements of the system). Results showed that many users (especially those not knowing the island of Santorini) lost orientation inside the environment. One user who had already experienced VR for playing games, suggested to include a ‘mini-map’ to improve the orientation. The related tool was then implemented in December 2024, after the survey that had been run during the Maldives summer school in November 2024. The mini-map is shown in Figs. 15a and 15b, with location of the user within the model and the direction of the movement of the user (like for a GPS in a car), which indeed helps now the user to get oriented within the immersive geographic environment. Also ‘clicking’ sound was added to the experience.

Figure 15. a – d) 3D views of the immersive environment created for Santorini, using the Cesium background imagery and surface model, here shown as ‘mixed’ reality model (as elements of the surrounding laboratory room are seen), complemented by the menu tool and mini map (for orientation and location); see also the Minoan volcanic deposit depth colons in (c), and the sea floor in (d).

A video of the Santorini VR (AR) experience can be found at:

https://www.georisk.uliege.be/cms/c_4823285/en/georisk?id=c_4823285

4) References

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Annex 6.1

Table 1: Survey results from the Erasmus+ Maldives school where students and professors experienced in VR with proper toolkit (Oculus) the Santorini model.

Participant Nr	M/F	Feeling (comfortable, vertigo?)	Compared with screen view (eg Google Earth)?	compared with GIS maps?	What else in immersive environments (what are you still missing)?
1M		comfortable, start from ground	clearly more than screen (2D) view	more effect.	labels (geog info, problem of connection with tutor... (does not see where you are) + start 2
2M		comfortable, because experience with VR with better resolution, better than OE	with better resolution, better than OE	better if geographic orientation better (did not know Santorini)	geographic guide (with map)- navigation help
3M		sight vertigo - no experience	different from OE. Feeling of being there	thinks more possible than with GIS - 3D	try map for orientation, but own control... Support guide + avatar accompanying
4F		no vertigo - comfortable	other experience than OE	more potential than GIS	something to get oriented, + walking + on ground movement, some inside helping person
5M		sight vertigo when fast	not big difference with OE, but still immersive experience	maybe interactive of GIS, maybe more potential than GIS...	sound might good... Noise of waves ++ explanations by someone like on plane
6F		sight vertigo effect... Fast... Experienced vertigo in reality	to be there feeling, more real... Not cartography - You can reach an object	maybe more potential, maybe "I don't know". But in VR maybe more maybe with sound + daylight... do something you cannot do otherwise in reality	
7F		no vertigo - little experience (at local points), helps to be in mixed reality	way better than OE	competitive with GIS if you can add geographic information	labels, sound, compass,
8F		sight dizzy, but less than other experience	different, but immersive is good. But not too long - OE more suitable for eyes	depends on main goal... Cannot replace GIS programs in 2D... In front of screen feels more comfortable	tools for measurements of distances, an outcomp, compass, map tool,
9F		no dizziness, or vertigo, little VR experience (local)	potential to improve the OE feeling in VR	possibility to be similar to GIS	local experience in general environment experience can be nice
10F		VR experience only at school - at school work, sometimes a bit dizzy	experiences different, flying, but otherwise similar,	more effect more than GIS... No expert in GIS	scale of depth of coast, no other comments
11M		beginning uncomfortable	similarity, no other comment	not familiar with GIS - 3D, no clear comparison possible	reviewing not perfect but slow (WF)
12F		no experience... Vertigo (but not afraid), dizzy,	similar but possible to go below surface might be more interesting than OE for geological mapping	no GIS experience, comparison difficult	software color - photography missing, labels (especially for people not knowing Santorini), points to be selected
14A	F - senior	no vertigo effect		mapping coordinates missing	how to visualize points, these coordinates are missing, points
15 S.	M - senior	vertigo effect			

Deliverable 6.2

Story Map – Coastal Geohazards of Mt. Etna

⇒ Story Map – Etna Region: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4067a77d69fd4d5e8ea7af3f9bfbbdb9>